

CRITICAL GNC ASPECTS FOR ADR MISSIONS

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ABSTRACT

In the past decade, GMV has been, both as a participant and a reviewer, at the forefront of ESA's efforts in identifying and responding to criticalities in GNC technologies for future ADR and in-orbit servicing missions.

This paper provides an anthology of the recent developments - the state of the art of ADR mission design from a GNC perspective, informed from GMV's recent experience in the topic. In addition to outlining some of the main challenges and describing the state-of-the-art of GNC responses, it outlines consolidated methodologies for design, development, verification and validation to advance of their readiness.

The know-how to inform GMV's critical assessment was acquired in mission development activities, from flagship initiatives to large targets to CubeSat in-orbit demonstrators; as well technological development programmes for specific elements, in particular, lessons learnt from GMV's predominant role in Mission Analysis and GNC design of ESA's e.Deorbit, RACE, MSRN, ORCO, COMRADE, DETUMBLING, COBRA, MSR-DD, D4R and ANDROID.

Some of GNC Critical Aspects within ADR missions covered are: concepts of operations; guidance - angular synchronization, passive safety trajectory planning; control – coupled, compliant and combined control, 6 DOF force motion control during synchronization phases, visual servoing and compliant 10+DoF control during reach, phase rate damping; multi-spectral / camera-only-based navigation.

1 INTRODUCTION TO THE STATE OF THE ART AND GMV HERITAGE

Never in the history of space exploitation has it been attempted the orbital capture and manipulation of a derelict, or otherwise non-collaborative, non-cooperative 3rd-party target satellite.

Novel Challenge – Proximity and Capture of an uncontrolled target

In close proximity lie the highest challenges - In close proximity, agility and precision in coupled position and attitude control are critical to ensure an operation free of collisions between the servicer and the target (and protruding elements in their structures – asymmetries, antennae, solar arrays, and the capture device itself). Careful assessment of relative position and attitude dynamics and selection of pose/trajectory references for approach (and collision-avoidance) pose a challenge to the guidance system. Flexible elements of the servicer, movable devices whose dynamics are inter-coupled (servicer, target, capture mechanism) and the need to manoeuvre in fixed positions in target body frame pose a challenge to the control, which must concurrently handle relative translation and relative attitude, in both inertial, synodic and target-body-fixed reference frames. The problem does not end

after the contact. The loads endured by the capture mechanism must be limited by the attitude control system to avoid damage, and a carefully stack de-tumble manoeuvre must be performed. The autonomous control system must be designed taking into account uncertainties in the inertia and load limits in the stack structure.

In the past decade, GMV has been, both as a core participant in ESA's activities, and through internal knowledge and infrastructure development and commercial activities, at the forefront of European efforts in identifying and responding to criticalities in GNC technologies for future ADR and in-orbit servicing missions, with focus on close proximity challenges. These advances are not limited to the GNC engineering itself, but also novel methodologies for design, development, verification and validation to advance of their readiness.

In parallel to reaching considerable maturity in collaborative formation-flying (spearheaded by PROBA3 mission, where GMV is leading the Formation Flying GNC S/S development, currently in phase D) and rendez-vous, ESA has promoted and concentrated efforts to TRL raising for technologies that tackle proximity challenges. GMV has been at the core of these efforts by leading their GNC component development – through the Clean Space initiative, and particularly its flagship e.Deorbit mission; and through several development activities and infrastructure for specific technological elements (such as COMRADE [1] – advance robust control and FDIR concepts for proximity ; DETUMBLING [2] – which specifically addressed the post-capture stack phases; and NGT-ATB where GMV updated ESTEC's own Avionics Testbed Laboratorial infrastructure for ADR GNC SW testing up to HIL).

While e.Deorbit has been ESA's flagship activity to deorbit Envisat in the last decade, RACE focused on CubeSats for in-orbit demonstration, ORCO[3] and COMRADE investigated and consolidated the complex couplings between the different control systems (GNC including image processing and robotics) for autonomous capture, derived required algorithms and performed HW-in-the-loop end-to-end demonstration. COMRADE focused on fully combined control for the operations of grasping, stabilisation and hold of the debris with the aim to perform the controlled de-orbit, as an alternative to decoupled and collaborative options - to overcome the problem of arbitrary, case-tailored control authority. MSRN investigated usage of the non-visible spectrum to tackle challenges like eclipses and early detection. DETUMBLING addressed de-tumbling strategies, particularly robust control for robotic arm capture but also contactless detumbling, which was the main subject of COBRA. D4R investigate technologies to facilitate the removal in targets to be launched in the future.

AnDROiD [4] was a first iteration of application of lessons learnt in a proposed small scale missions focusing on the feasibility of removing small debris objects, while testing on orbit at least two different capture techniques before the actual deorbiting of the target, a net and a robotic arm. AnDROiD would use PROBA-NEXT platform and would employ the advanced aforementioned GNC techniques with Proba-2 as a target. Focus was given to system-level and mission-level aspects and scalability.

This paper critically summarizes the advances and conclusions of these activities – it compiles in a critical analysis the state of the art of GMV's ADR lessons learnt from a GMV's perspective.

2 – CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

Critical challenges within ADR missions have been identified and further in GMV's recent drive : concepts of operations; guidance - angular synchronization, passive safety trajectory planning; control – coupled, compliant and combined control , precise attitude control during boosts, 6 DOF forced motion control during synchronization phases, advanced coupling between platform 6DOF control and capture device reach; stack phase rate damping and MCI estimation; camera-based and data-fusion navigation – image processing from acquisition and tracking through bearings-only navigation to model-based pose estimation; operations control authority and autonomy levels, modes management; software and GNC architectures, DDVV cycles.

2.1 – Concepts of operations

Internationally accepted standards for orbital proximity operations are being drafted and consolidated - ESA is deriving a set of consolidated guidelines to be harmonized to the global standards and definitions (eg. CONFERS)[5].

Namely, nomenclatures for the phases of the rendez-vous and capture process and their thresholds are based on the level of autonomy, engagement of sensors and observables of the navigation system, objective and methods of the GNC.

It is thus useful to introduce definitions - rendez-vous and capture is split into phases: **Orbit Phasing** (commanded by ground), **Closing** (autonomous or semi-autonomous, based on coarse relative metrology, often bearings-only navigation), **Proximity** (Fly-Around, Motion Synchronization) and **Capture**.

From the GNC architecture apportioning of functions, authority and and modes particular perspective we introduce the nomenclature for further segmentation (sub-) phases,

- **Final Approach/Close Proximity:** forced-motion (as opposed to impulsive) tracking of a reference guidance profile (dynamic or station-keeping), making use of the precise modes of the navigation (eg.: relative pose estimation). This operational phase may employ two modes in the GNC:
 - **Forced translation** - The GNC operates in local orbital reference frame, the GNC control of position and velocity is performed separately from the AOCS (there might however be some coupling at guidance level ie, interfaces exist when target-pointing attitude mode is activated).
 - **Synchronization** - The GNC operates in target body reference frame, and 6 DoF fully combined control takes command of both translation and attitude. Its fundamental objective is synchronizing the translational and rotational motion of the servicer with that of the target. In a sub-mode, **rate matching**, the servicer rotates along the instantaneous rotation axis of the target with the same angular rate.

Note that configuration changes, such as limitation of the RCS authority to avoid impingement, or final commissioning/deployment of the capture device may occur during this phase, quickly changing the inertia properties of the platform and thus requiring adjustments in control.

- **Engagement and Rigidization** activation of the capture device without overpassing the load limits of the structure.
- **Stack Phase** where the servicer and target are attached. Like in synchronization, the G&C commands attitude and attitude in 6DoF, in Inertial and/or Local Reference frames, acting like a unitary module. It comprises subphases:
 - **Detumbling** - angular stabilization on the stack system composed by the servicer, the target object and the rigidized capture device tentacles.
 - **De-Orbiting** – engagement of thrust for removal from orbit

Figure 1: Operations Sequence – ESA/Airbus' e.Deorbit (from) as commented a template

Thus, rendez-vous problem with a non-cooperating target can be broadly divided into far-range (closing), mid-range (fly-around), final approach (forced translation and synchronization), stack phases (detumbling and deorbiting). **Figure 1: Operations Sequence – ESA/Airbus' e.Deorbit (from) as commented a template** presents, as an example, a rendez-vous and capture operational timeline – the established plan by Airbus [6],[7] e.Ddeorbit is superimposed with the GMV's aforementioned definitions to illustrate broadness of applicability.

2.2 – Phasing, Far-range Approach, Closing,

During phasing, based on ground measurements and target orbit determination results, a passively safe relative orbit is acquired – this orbit is known as the rendezvous entry gate. The closing/far-range stage starts after the target is detected and the relative navigation system is commissioned and engaged .

Missionization/ground-based and on-board homing trajectory optimization must be performed that optimizes full state observability from bearings only navigation. Interfaces between navigation, guidance and collision-avoidance monitoring must be in place (GUIBEAR [8]: Guidance for bearings-only navigation is recently finalized ESA/GMV activity to address ground-based and on-board model-predictive control methods for a guidance solution that optimizes propellant consumption and observability for navigation accuracy while ensuring a collision-free approach). An inclination-eccentricity orbital separation (*spiral*) approach manoeuvre may be applied to bring the chaser to a park hold-point defined at a safe distance to the target on the V-bar.

After commissioning period during which the navigation filter converges, a series of manoeuvres, based on safe-orbits, are performed to bring the chaser to closer to the target, typically employing a safe hold-points. The mid-range operational concept is equivalent to the fly-around phase, which performs relative navigation using ranging and LoS measurements.

Impulsive radial manoeuvres and passive safety through from the perspective of autonomous GNC and ground operations are at this point a standard in any formation flying mission and rendez-vous mission. The novel challenge (and risk) from the Guidance Navigation and Control perspective starts upon commissioning of the full 6DoF relative pose (position and attitude) estimation of the chaser with respect to the target.

2.3 Synchronization - Collision-free Guidance and Control

Rigid-link capture strategies may require the chaser to synchronize its attitude and translation motion with a tumbling target.

Before the capture/synchronization begins, the target debris object is inspected from a safe orbit to determine mass properties, configuration and possible damage to the structure. This information is used in the planning of the subsequent phases.

The attitude synchronization manoeuvre takes the servicer from an initial position in the LVLH frame with a target-pointing attitude to a static position in the target body frame, with an attitude defined with respect to the target body frame. Depending on the capture method, the servicer may need to accurately synchronize its motion with the target and maintain synchronization while reducing the relative distance.

Torque-free attitude motion is governed by four constants of motion, namely, the kinetic energy and the three components of the angular momentum vector. The angular momentum vector is constant in inertia space, but in the spacecraft body frame the components of the angular momentum vector are time-dependent. The magnitude of the angular momentum vector is constant, however, meaning that the possible values of the angular momentum vector components lie on a sphere. The rotational kinetic energy determines another constraint.

The assumption of quasi-torque-free motion is exploited by defining an approach strategy over the angular momentum vector. When approaching a target in free-attitude motion over the angular momentum vector a plane perpendicular to the angular momentum vector can be defined that guarantees a collision-free approach down to a certain specific distance. The attitude motion of Envisat in inertial space can be visualized using Poinsot's construction [9]. Poinsot observed that the rotation of a body in space can be described as the inertia ellipsoid rolling without slipping along a stationary plane perpendicular to the angular momentum vector.

The inertia ellipsoid rolls along an invariant plane without slipping. Figure 2 illustrates this idea. The angular momentum vector of the body is shown as a blue arrow, the angular velocity vector as a red arrow and the trajectory of the angular velocity on the inertia ellipsoid as a red curve. Also shown in red is the trajectory traced out by the angular velocity vector on the invariant plane.

A collision-free approach over the angular momentum vector can be guaranteed by defining an ellipsoid congruent to the inertia ellipsoid that contains the target spacecraft. This ellipsoid touches an invariable plane at a specific distance from the target centre of mass; above this distance the approach is guaranteed to be collision-free.

Figure 2: Left - Example of synchronization manoeuvre , Right - Free attitude motion

A guidance function has been developed for the attitude synchronization with the target debris object, Envisat. The spin synchronization occurs just before capturing the target with a robotic arm. The guidance function prepares a reference trajectory and attitude profile and feed-forward forces and torques. Figure 2 shows an overview of the synchronization manoeuvre. The synchronization sequence consists of the following steps:

- Station-keeping on V-bar,
- Approach over V-bar from a distance of 50 m to 30 m,
- Transfer to the angular momentum vector of the target at 30 m
- Approach over angular momentum vector to 6.5 m and synchronize attitude with target
- Transfer into body frame to the instantaneous angular momentum velocity vector, maintaining attitude synchronization
- Step 6: Transfer to terminal approach direction in target body fixed frame
- Step 7: Linear approach from 6.5 m to terminal approach point and attitude

This guidance strategy has been tested and deemed feasible to successfully capture Envisat taking into account the constraints of the propulsion system and the mass of the chaser spacecraft.

Control Techniques

In the synchronization phase a 6DoF controller must ensure an accurate trajectory tracking. The vibration mode dynamics from sloshing, bending modes, reaction-wheel behaviour uncertainties, and non-modelled dynamics will have significant effects on the stability and performance of the controlled vehicle. The driving parameters for control selection are

- Uncertain vibration mode damping due to propellant sloshing – amplification of the transfer function magnitude relates with the flexible mode damping ratio. Small damping generates large resonance gain. The damping coefficient is never known with high accuracy
- Couplings between axes – vibration modes introduce couplings between control axes that can cause problems in the control design
- MCI, actuation and sensor uncertainties – MCI properties are known up to a certain interval and can be changing over time due to propellant consumption. Actuation models and sensors are also approximations
- Navigation errors
- Delay in the navigation filter
- Actuation allocation – The system is over-actuated by RCS, RW and MTQ – the controller shall optimize the usage of the available actuators given the different characteristics of each
- The system is a Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) dynamic system

Requirements specification is quite straightforward for synthesis techniques in the frequency domain such as H_∞ based techniques. Disturbance and noise rejection problems are naturally formulated in the frequency domain since these phenomena can have their spectrum characterized. The statement of a steady state error requirement and the specification of the transient response characteristics via the control bandwidth are also convenient. Moreover, the robust control design can further be verified using analytical methods such as μ -analysis prior to the V&V campaign allowing to have a higher confidence in the resulting controller.

In H_∞ related methods, the requirements specification information is included within scaling factors and weighting functions (of MIMO nature), which are used to augment the plant model entering the synthesis process.

Figure 3: Augmented Plant Model [1]

The purpose of the weighting functions is to impose a desired boundary on the associated input to output transfer function. These boundaries are chosen such that the feedback control has the desired properties in order to meet the design objectives. For example, the weights W_S and W_T can be used to shape the Sensitivity transfer function S and Complementary Sensitivity transfer function T , respectively.

The weights $W(s)$ are MIMO filters which shape the frequency of the different signals, where the inputs are shaped to resemble the excitation frequencies, and the outputs are shaped for the desired closed-loop behaviour.

The weights D are constants which scale the magnitude of the different signals. The plant P contains the plant without dimensions, so in order to accommodate the signals for H_∞ synthesis, the input/output signals are scaled by different factors. This approach is similar to having a scaling function and an inverse scaling function before and after the plant, but removes the need of scaling the resulting controller to the problem dimensions, and allows to define each scaling factor independently of the other weights or the shaping weight. The scaling is performed as follows:

- Input signals \tilde{d} , \tilde{r} and \tilde{n} are multiplied respectively by the disturbance level, the maximum tracking step and the noise level. This way, the signals enter with real values into both the plant and the controller.
- Output signals e and y are divided by the maximum error, and the signal u is divided by the maximum available actuation. This scales back from real dimensions to non-dimensional unitary magnitudes, in order to have a representative value of the resulting γ from the synthesis process.

An additional navigation block $N(s)$ can be added to the model. This function forces the separation between two different error signals, one real error that uses measurements from the plant and is used in the loop-shaping, and one error with respect to the navigation filter, which is used as input to the controller channel.

Figure 4: H_∞ mixed sensitivity design strategy [1]

The selection of the weights for H_∞ controller design is an important step of control design in a mixed-sensitivity H_∞ framework. Table below provides a generic rationale for starting this process, which is followed by iterative fine tuning for the desired time domain performance, as well as robust stability and performance.

Table 1: Generic rationale for H_∞ weight selection

Weight	Low Frequency gain	High Frequency gain	Natural Frequency	Type	
Outputs	$W_S(s)$	Desired tracking	Limit overshoot	Close loop time constant	LP filter
	$W_T(s)$	$S + T = 1$	Sensor noise rejection	$S + T = 1$	HP filter
	$W_u(s)$	1	HF control rejection	Control bandwidth / noise frequencies	HP filter
Inputs	$W_d(s)$	1	$\ll 1$	Model known disturbances	LP filter
	$W_r(s)$	1 (tracking)	High attenuation	$> w_S$	LP filter
	$W_n(s)$	Power spectral density of measurement noise			LP filter

It should be noted that, in mixed sensitivity synthesis the order of the resulting controller is equal to the order of the open loop system and the sum of the order of all the weights. This means that setting n –order weights to all the 6 signals would raise the controller order by $48n$. Furthermore, enforcing

too many restrictions on the signals may result in some difficulty to find a controller, or in it failing robust stability and/or performance tests.

One of the particularities of the servicer vehicle is the availability of RCS thrusters and RW. The system is then over-actuated by actuators with different characteristics. On one hand RCS can generate much higher torques than the RW, but on the other hand, RCS have a slower dynamic response and the Minimum Impulse Bit results in minimum forces and torques that can limit the pointing accuracy. One possible strategy to optimize the usage of the different available actuators is through the weight $W_u(s)$. The plant is modified in order to include both control signals and, it is possible to split $W_u(s)$ into $W_{u_{RCS}}(s)$ and $W_{u_{RW}}(s)$ that specify the saturation values and the cut-off frequencies of the RCS thrusters and RW, respectively.

After the synthesis, the μ -analysis method allows to assess the robust stability and robust performance of the generated controller. μ -analysis relies on the system uncertainty representation by means of Linear Fractional Transformations (LFTs). The LFT approach allows a system representation in which the uncertainty perturbations are approximated by a block diagonal matrix Δ . With the increasing number of parametric uncertainties, μ -synthesis methods can become computationally heavy and the obtained results are conservative which obstruct the fulfillment of the performance requirements. Thus, the parametric uncertainties are not considered at synthesis level. The preferred approach aims at achieving the synthesis on the nominal system, and then at checking the robustness and performance through μ -analysis. If the analysis is satisfying, then the controller is approved and the synthesis stops. Otherwise, the process is repeated iteratively with re-tuned weights, until the closed-loop achieves the stability and performance requirements for all the uncertainty combinations. The μ -analysis routine depends on the number of uncertainties and their occurrence, and can also be a very slow process however it is usually faster than running a Monte Carlo campaign. However it only tests the combinations of uncertainties that are considered in the model used for control design that is simplified and does not include environment effects, navigation filter in the loop etc. Thus, the μ -analysis does not replace a proper V&V campaign.

2.4 Closure and Capture

In the final steps, the challenge of handling in presence of flexible elements and fuel sloshing with uncertain properties (the latter are particularly challenging to determine in advance of the operation) is further raised by the need to address the mechanisms such as those of the capture device and the solar array gimbals, which introduce couplings between translation and rotation states and the mathematical model (including multi-body models) is only partially known. Moreover, proximity manoeuvring impose stringent performance requirements to the control system that must be considered at control synthesis level. Again, advanced robust control techniques that allow to formulate disturbance and noise rejection problems in the frequency domain have been applied and successfully tested GMV to the synthesis and analysis of controllers for the most critical phases.

These final steps in closure and capture present most of the main challenges for the control system. Because the servicer's translation is being commanded in the target body frame at a comparatively large distance from the centre of mass, large accelerations are required from the propulsion system. This phase requires, concurrently, a careful setting of reference range for the manoeuvres (apportioned according to the control authority of the propulsion system); and a design of a controller with higher bandwidth but at the same time capable of guaranteeing at all times that unstabilizing modes from flexible elements, such as sloshing, solar-arrays, among others, are not excited. Indeed, one of the main difficulties in the control design of spacecraft is not so much the flexible modes themselves but rather the fact that their properties are uncertain. Models of flexible appendages are always only partly representative of the true dynamics. If the properties of the flexible modes were exactly known then it would be a simple process to either notch them out with a filter or to invert the plant in the controller.

The problem of capturing the target with mechanical articulated devices, after the synchronization manoeuvre (if needed) has been tackled using independent controllers for the servicer base and capture mechanism and by applying different compliant control techniques. In ORCO, the manipulator controller was based on visual-servo control while the chaser spacecraft featured a translational-rotational high-precision robust 6DoF controller for the platform; in e.Deorbit, visual servoing was tested to guide the ensemble to the capture position via 6 DOF POSE estimates of the Target by means of 3D model matching; and in DETUMBLING [2] a full 10DOF robust combined H_∞ controller was designed and tested in a high-fidelity simulation scenario. The controller included weights in the synthesis-level that allowed to limit the loads and issuing commands to the capture device and to the chaser propulsion system. Nonlinear compliant control techniques are also relevant – these were applied in COMRADE and e.Deorbit activities: in the former, a 13 DOF force/torque compliant control was designed and tested till HIL level; in the latter, a 6 DOF cartesian force/torque compliant control was used during the clamping operation to ensure that during the device engagement forces and torques (especially acting on the grappling tentacles) are kept within a certain limit and that the device is not damaged. After the capture, if the coupled system is tumbling, the chaser must keep actuating to avoid large loads on linking system. This problem has been addressed in the referred activities with specially designed GNC mode designed to slow down and deorbit the coupled system while limiting the loads.

Several methodologies for control design have been established as practical engineering design tools: from the dependable but classical linear quadratic regulator design, to more advanced techniques such as H_∞ robust control (mixed sensitivity, loop shaping - four blocks approach, D-K and D-G-K iteration), Nonlinear dynamic inversion (force and moment approach, inner and outer loop design), Quantitative Feedback Theory, Model Predictive Control, Sliding mode control, as well as combinations and variations of these techniques.

H_∞ Mixed-Sensitivity is now a mature approach that was applied to solve the synchronization problem in COMRADE and ORCO [3] where a TRL 5 was achieved, and also in many activities such as e.Deorbit [6],[7], DETUMBLING, and NRO-GNC. It is therefore the most promising candidate approach to the overall control design.

In the e.Deorbit mission consolidation phase, where the large GEO servicer *SpaceTug* was being considered for capture and de-orbiting a tumbling Envisat from LEO, GMV concluded that the system did not have control authority to perform the synchronization at the required rotation rate. After a thorough analysis, the torques and forces necessary to perform the station keeping in target body frame were concluded that not achievable by the propulsion system authority. It was not possible to reduce the distance from the centre of mass of the target due to the protruding elements of the target. Therefore this limitation resulted in the definition of a maximum target rotation rate at which the synchronization was possible with that servicer propulsion system.

Figure 5: Maximum Force and Torque Envelopes for Synchronization (e.Deorbit C)

In 2017, ESA/GMV's ORCO activity developed a complete GNC for rendezvous and deorbit a small target debris, achieving a TRL of 5. The GNC architecture included H_∞ robust controllers and a model-based tracking navigation algorithm. The GNC was implemented and deployed onboard a chaser mockup that featured a custom vision system with a dedicated FPGA to aid in the image processing. HIL results were obtained in *platform-art*®, see Figure 6.

On ORCO project, one of major factors influencing the performance of the GNC was the capture device - the follow-up COMRADE activity was consequently devoted to explore a fully combined control solution. The VV process included PIL/HIL tests and resulted in a TRL raise to 5/6. The solution consists of a control system with high improvement potential (propellant saving, performances increase, safety) due to the null-space movements' possibilities provided by the added degrees-of-freedom. Using a robotic capture device mounted on the servicer, the target is grappled and a rigidization phase follows in which the joint breaks are engaged. Stabilization/de-tumbling is performed while both spacecraft are linked through the rigidized manipulator.

The synchronization phase was handled by an H_∞ 6DOF robust controller over a rigid body with modelled sloshing and flexibility (solar arrays, stored robotic manipulator) effects.

Advanced FDA/FTC techniques have also been considered as an additional Failure Detection and Accommodation layer on top of the nominal control design.

C code has been produced from GNC MIL models using auto-coding techniques plus some hand-made corrections. The obtained GNC OBSW has been downloaded into a space-representative processor including RTEMS and Leon4 architecture. Finally, different tests cases (sub-set from the MIL test plan) covering all relevant scenario phases and all relevant controllers implementation have been tested within the PIL environment for Verification and Validation purposes of the GNC OBSW[10].

Figure 6: Navigation and relative pose estimation using visual camera with a non-cooperative satellite (PROBA2 mockup) during ESA ORCO project tests

After the synchronization (if any), the capture mechanism shall be deployed and then a capture manoeuvre is performed to grasp the target forming a physical link between the two bodies.

After confirmation of successful capture, if the capture mechanism is composed by one or more robotic arms/devices, the joints are rigidized. The arms should be operated in impedance control mode and are stiffened until the joint rates are low enough to engage the joint brakes.

Depending on the MCI properties and rotational state of the target and chaser it may be necessary to maintain active the relative orbit and attitude control system during the de-tumbling – stabilization phase. The rationale for this approach is that it enables the forces and torques on the capture/contact points to be controlled more precisely. Just before the chaser grabs the target, the forces and torques on the capture points are zero (that is, the capture has not taken place yet). Just after capture, the forces and torques on the interface points should remain small as the chaser continues to control its relative position and attitude with respect to the target.

After capture, the chaser starts computing the feed-forward torque required to de-tumble the target while respecting a maximum force and torque limit endured on the contact points. The feed-forward torque is computed as if the chaser is not attached to the target. The chaser GNC provides the thruster acceleration required to remain stationary in the target body frame plus the thruster acceleration required to provide the desired force and torque at the capture points.

The control design for this phase can be simplified to 3DoF, as the main goal is to reduce the rotational kinetic energy. On the other hand, the model is highly uncertain due to errors in the capture position and unknown properties of the target. Moreover, new sources of flexible elements may come in play for example in the capture mechanism. Also for this phase, H_{∞} Mixed-Sensitivity was successfully used in past projects such as COMRADE and DETUMBLING.

In DETUMBLING, an additional stabilization controller was designed to de-tumble the composite of the servicer and target, actuating on the servicer and using as feedback the loads on the capture mechanism. Although the controller was able to reduce the loads, the feed-forward command from the guidance is always necessary to avoid high initial loads. In COMRADE an extra phase is used before the capture, the reach phase – where a gripper is moved to grasping position based on visual servoing.

Advanced Control techniques: Visual Servoing and Compliant Control

The problem of capture the target with a robotic arm, after the synchronization manoeuvre has been tackled using independent controllers for the chaser base and robotic manipulator and by applying different compliant control techniques. In ORCO the manipulator controller is based on visual-servo control while the chaser spacecraft features a high-precision robust 6DoF controller. In e.Deorbit visual servoing would be used to guide the robotic arm to the capture position via 6 DOF POSE estimates of the by means of 3D model matching. In DETUMBLING a full 10DoF robust H_∞ controller was designed and tested in a high-fidelity simulation scenario. The controller included in the synthesis-level weights that allow to limit the joint loads and issues commands to the robotic arm joints and to the chaser propulsion system. Nonlinear compliant control techniques were applied in COMRADE and e.Deorbit activities. In the latter, a 6 DoF cartesian force/torque compliant control of the robotic arm is used during the clamping operation. The goal of the compliant control is to ensure that during the motion of the arm the forces and torques (especially acting on the gripper) are kept within a certain limit and that the gripper, the robotic arm and the clamp are not damaged.

The chaser spacecraft often includes flexible elements and fuel sloshing with uncertain properties (the latter are particularly challenging to determine in advance of the operation). These, together with elements such as robotic manipulators, end-effectors and clamping mechanisms, introduce couplings between translation and rotation states and the mathematical model is only partially known. Moreover, proximity manoeuvring impose stringent performance requirements to the control system that must be considered at synthesis level. Advanced robust control techniques that allow to formulate disturbance and noise rejection problems in the frequency domain were applied by GMV to the synthesis and analysis of controllers for the most critical phases.

One of the most recently adopted control synthesis methodologies (edeorbit, comrade, IOA-GNC, ...) is H_∞ Mixed Sensitivity Design [3]. Its synthesis process aims at shaping the sensitivity functions in order to achieve the closed-loop system performance and robustness requirements. Moreover, the sensitivity function shaping is achieved with frequency varying weights (of MIMO nature). The weight selection as well as the robust stability and performance analysis follows the process in [2].

Such H_∞ synthesis method [11],[12] requires an LFT representation of the linearized flexible spacecraft model so that the plant model can consider parametric variations. An accurate and straightforward modelling technique of a multi-body system is the Two-Input Two-Output Port (TITOP) [13] shows the chaser spacecraft instantiation. The hub TITOP starts from its rigid dynamics, with uncertainty on mass and inertia parameters, and is expanded to connect to two child elements: slosh modes, and solar panel flexible modes.

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Figure 7: Chaser model based on TITOP models

In e.Deorbit visual servoing would be used to guide the robotic arm to the capture position via 6 DOF POSE estimates of the by means of 3D model matching. In DETUMBLING a full 10DoF robust H_∞ controller was designed and tested in a high-fidelity simulation scenario. The controller included in the synthesis-level weights that allow to limit the joint loads and issues commands to the robotic arm joints and to the chaser propulsion system. Nonlinear compliant control techniques were applied in COMRADE and e.Deorbit activities. In the latter, a 6 DoF cartesian force/torque compliant control of the robotic arm is used during the clamping operation. The goal of the compliant control is to ensure that during the motion of the arm the forces and torques (especially acting on the gripper) are kept within a certain limit and that the gripper, the robotic arm and the clamp are not damaged.

During aforementioned activities GMV has acquired experience on multi-body dynamics required for modelling robotic arm and moving end-effector manipulators (probes, grippers), as well as on contact dynamics occurring with target bodies.

This modelling infrastructure ensures V&V test coverage at Model-In-the-Loop (MIL), Functional Engineering Simulation (FES) level, both software testbenches, of both visual servoing and compliant control strategies. GMV has proven experience translating such algorithms into subsequent testbenches, i.e. Software-In-the-Loop (SIL), Processor-In-the-Loop (PIL), and Hardware-In-the-Loop (HIL).

Specifically, *platform-art*© is GMV's test facility designed/developed to provide verification and validation capabilities (through real dynamics generation to stimulate due HW) of Guidance, Navigation and Control (GNC) systems for short range phases of rendezvous, formation flying and ADR missions, as far as other relative scenarios such as planetary or asteroid landing. On-board sensors and on-board computers and algorithms are connected to a real world simulator that in turn operates the robots tracking the simulated relative pose, which is measured by the on-board sensors and algorithms, closing the GNC loop. An automated lighting system in a dark room permits obtaining realistic space environment images during the tests

The maturity level of GNC systems is raised by methodically increasing fidelity and representativeness of the testing setup. With *platform-art*© the maturity level of GNC systems can be raised at HIL up to TRL5/6.

3 Other Recent Technology Developments Applicable to ADR

3.1 Contactless Detumbling

The propulsion system of the servicer spacecraft may not have enough control authority to effectively perform the synchronization maneuver. The Target's angular velocity and the distance at which the synchronization begins - which, in turn, depends on the physical size of the target - can claim large maneuvers which may not be possible to perform due to the limitations of the propulsion system.

Contactless de-tumbling methods have the advantage that they can impart low structural loads on the target, can operate at a distance outside of the envelope of the target motion, and can slow down the target rotation rate significantly within a reasonable amount of time.

Plume impingement is one of the contactless de-tumbling techniques that consists of the impingement of a gas jet from a thruster located on the servicer. Some recent studies have addressed this problem.

COBRA [14] proposed Active Debris Removal (ADR) using plume impingement from a hydrazine monopropellant propulsion system to impart a ΔV of 50m/s on a 100kg target object.

The plume impingement concept was proposed and studied in e-Deorbit as a consequence of the limited propulsion capabilities of the servicer spacecraft. In this study, ENVISAT (the target debris) was tumbling at a predicted rate of 2.5 deg/s. Several scenarios were tested in simulation

The study shows that, in four hours, is possible reduce the angular rate of the target down to a value that enables the synchronization without the need to change the propulsion system.

Table 1 - Results of Plume Impingement Monte-Carlo campaign

	After 4 hours				After 8 hours			
	Mean	σ	Min	Max	Mean	σ	Min	Max
$\ \omega\ $ (deg/s)	0.41	0.30	0.07	1.13	0.40	0.28	0.06	1.11
Angle wrt XY	3.17	28.6	-69.9	76.6	0.41	31.3	-88.8	89.9
Angle wrt XZ	-0.10	26.7	-67.8	78.3	0.61	30.4	-78.7	90.0

At the end of the detumbling phase, the target's angular rate shows the following characteristics:

- Average magnitude of 0.4 deg/s with a 1-sigma dispersion of 0.3 deg/s.
- Average direction of the x-axis of the Target's Body-Frame (positive or negative) with 30 degrees of 1-sigma dispersion.

The average impingement ΔV to detumble the target is shown to be low with low dispersion over the Monte Carlo tests. Even in the most demanding runs, the impingement ΔV did not pass the 3.5m/s. This is an indication that, given a favorable positioning of the chaser with respect to the spin axis of the target, it would require low effort and time to perform the detumble.

A relevant conclusion of the study was that the possibility of moving the chaser to favorable relative positions with respect to the target, e.g. to points perpendicular to the spin axis of the target, would maximize the effects of the plume impingement.

3.2 Model Predictive Control and On-Board Optimization

In the ongoing NRO-GNC and NRO-GUIBEAR activities, the main challenges are:

- Modelling the effects of propellant sloshing, and designing robust controllers that could handle the unmodelled disturbances, but more specifically avoid the impact of sloshing on stability and performance.
- Dealing with large uncertainties in the MCI properties, that, in turn, caused larger uncertainties in the unstabilizing modes as well.
- The vision-based navigation introduces delays due to the computations required to obtain state estimates. These delays reduce stability margins. This has to be taken into account in the design.
- Trajectory optimization both on-board and off-line, that balances Δv consumption and observability while ensuring safety

The experience obtained in these activities is invaluable in the establishment of extensive know-how for control design in mission context, especially in advanced techniques and challenges such as the ones posed by robust design. The large variety of scenarios addressed, in terms of the disturbances affecting the spacecraft also provides a thorough pool of resources to tackle the many challenges in future activities.

The GUIBEAR project has demonstrated the combination of Model Predictive Control with bearings-only navigation for far-range rendezvous isfeasible from the point of view of the G&N. The current G&N design improves on the previously analysed approach to the end of the orbit transfer phase of the LAE when rendezvousing the LOP-G at the small added cost of a delta-V expenditure of few meters per second

3.3 Design For Removal (D4R)

Within the D4R activities, GMV is supporting ESA for designing devices that can be used after End Of Life (EoL) of second generation Copernicus platforms. In particular, GMV is giving support for the design of the 2D markers that will be placed in all the face of the platform and that will help to derive the satellite position and attitude in case of the need of a capture mission after EoL. The 2D markers are supposed to be used in a rendezvous and capture mission from a chaser satellite from 50 to 5 meters relative distance. On the other hand, the 2D markers will also include a small Laser Retro-Reflector (LRR) that can be tracked from ground Laser ranging station in order to improve the Orbit Determination accuracy in case of critical satellite failures. It is under discussion the possibility of combining the design of 2D markers that can be detected within different spectrum. In particular it is analysed the possibility of having markers that are visible within Visual and Near Infrared spectrum (VNIR) spectrum and Thermal Infrared (TIR) spectrum. One of the main difficulties of the activity is to extrapolate the evolution of the multispectral camera characteristics in the future. Another difficulty is the evolution of the material properties between Beginning Of Life (BoL) and after End Of Life (EoL). In this particular aspect, ESA is performing different aging campaign of materials that can be tested in the near future within Platform-art© laboratory at GMV in order to assess the possible loss of navigation performances between materials at BoL and EoL.

Additionally, GMV is supporting ESA for the design of 3D marker to be placed within the Launcher Adapter Ring (LAR). The 3D marker are supposed to be used in a rendezvous and capture mission from a chaser satellite from 5 meters to capture of the satellite. 3D marker will be a single marker that will be used during the capture and has to provide the sufficient navigation performance for allowing the capture. In particular GMV is supporting ESA for understanding if the surrounding material as Kapton can create some difficulty during the close approach of a capture mission. Within this analyses, GMV will be using Platform-art© laboratory in order to assess the possible loss of navigation performances between materials at BoL and EoL.

Figure 8 3D marker designed surrounded by Kapton (gold) seen at 1 meter distance

3.4 Multi Spectral Relative Navigation (MSRN)

Even though The MSRN mission scenario is based on the in the cooperative rendezvous scenario in the Heracles mission context its conclusions are applicable to ADR. The project focuses on the Vision Based Navigation making use of a multispectral camera providing images of different FOV in the Visible (VIS) band and in the Thermal Infrared Band (TIR).

MSRN2 image processing is composed of two algorithms devoted to different ranges. Close range vision based navigation needs higher accuracy level on the algorithm estimations with respect to far range navigation. A centroid algorithm was selected for far range, as angles-only navigation provides the accuracy needed for this phase of the trajectory. MBT algorithm was selected for close range as it is able of providing accurate position and attitude estimations during the last phase of the trajectory. Therefore, MSRN2 image processing is composed of these two algorithm implementations.

Centroids measurements are the base for angles only navigation. By measuring the line-of-sight and then the azimuth and elevation angles from some reference location (i.e. chaser) to another object (i.e. target) it is possible to determine the relative position and velocity between them. If the position and velocity of one of the points is known, then the position and velocity of the other can theoretically be deduced.

Model based tracking algorithm performs a pose estimation (position + attitude) based on the realignment of projected model edges with respect to the observed ones on the target. An improvement on the navigation data is produced by the used of MBT with respect to centroid algorithm as a pose estimation is provided, including an accurate range estimation, with respect to only-angles navigation where attitude and range cannot be provided.

MSRN2 technologies were assed during several test phases departing from laboratory rendered images to real VIS and TIR images captured in platform-art© robotic testbed. The analysis performed on the obtained results revealed the following findings:

- Image processing based on TIR band is able to provide a stable source of navigation data under different illumination conditions, with its associated thermal states. TIR images shall always provide a minimum contrast between the target surfaces and the surroundings as the spacecraft body temperature would be above space temperature.
- Image processing based on VNIR images produces accurate pose estimations under favourable illumination conditions, suffering under worst case scenario, where a reduced part of the target is visible.
- The combination of both image processing instances, VNIR and TIR, allows to obtain an accurate pose estimation at each moment, under different illumination and thermal situations.
- The existence of different fields of view in TIR and VNIR images has been revealed as an advantage for image processing. Larger target apparent size from VNIR images, in comparison with TIR ones, is an advantage at farther distances. On the other side, smaller target apparent size from TIR images is an advantage, with respect to VNIR images, during fly-around manoeuvre and during the last metres of the final approach.

Figure 9 MSRN Technologies being tested in platform-art©

4 CONCLUSION

The advances and conclusions reported in from technology development activities developed in the past decade by GMV with ESA – the application of systems’ theory/robust-control-based approach, heuristics-based guidance, vision-based navigation, with practical use cases haven in common that their development to a high level of maturity consolidation were brought about by a method of Model-based incremental Design Development Verification and Validation perfected by GMV - integrated, coherent and incremental DDVV approach concept based on the chain MIL (Model In the Loop) → Autocoding → SIL (SW In the Loop) → PIL T/B (Processor In the Loop Test Bench) → HIL T/B (HW In the Loop Test Bench), where GMV’s platform-art© facilities play a pivotal role.

The conclusions are many and may be found in the specific references. Some illustrative examples:

- Current synthetic Image Generation has been deemed insufficient with respect to mock-up laboratorial testing for Multi-Spectral-based optical navigation.
- The fuel sloshing has a significant impact on the control performance. Tank baffles shall be included to augment the damping coefficient.
- The uncertainty in the MCI properties further impacts the performance and must be estimated using dedicated observers, and accounted for in the control design. Concurrent identification and adaptive control must be employed (and validated).
- Moving parts shall be accounted for in control design, either by augmenting the degrees of freedom of the controller, or by considering the resulting change in MCI within the uncertainty envelope.

As a finishing remark: currently, aside from extending the currently presented TRL-5 technology to adjacent use cases (as is the case for In-Orbit Assembly) this DDVV process is in the process of being updated and applied to the new perspectives in spacecraft automatic controls: on-board optimization[8], machine learning [27] [28].

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